

Tingambato

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Entry tags: Archaeological Site, Mexican Religion, Religious Group, Language, Unknown, Religious Place, Tingambato

Tingambato was one of the most important archaeological cities in the area now occupied by the state of Michoacán during the Classic and Epiclassic periods. It was a large city of about 100 hectares of extension that in its core had pyramidal structures, large platforms, palace-like complexes and a large ball game. One of the most relevant characteristics was the construction of large tombs where important individuals rested and important offerings were placed.

Date Range: 0 CE - 900 CE

Region: Tingambato

Region tags: Mexico, West Mexico

The approximate limits of the city of Tingambato are located, including the nuclear part and the area open to the public.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Piña Chan, R., & Oi, K. (1982). *Exploraciones arqueológicas en Tingambato, Michoacán*. INAH.
- Source 2: Punzo-Díaz, J. L. (2022). Revisitando las exploraciones arqueológicas en el sitio de Tingambato, Michoacán: Nuevos datos, nuevas tecnologías. *Latin American Antiquity*, 33(1), 79–96. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2021.65>
- Source 3: Valdes Herrera, A., & Punzo, J. L. (2020). La Tumba II de Tingambato, Michoacán: un contexto funerario particular dentro de la Tradición de Tumbas de Cámara del Epiclásico. *Americae European Journal of Americanist Archaeology*.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.laiesken.net/arqueologia/archivo/2016/30/2_en
- Source 1 Description: The archaeological site of Tingambato is one of the few sites in Michoacán to have been extensively excavated, but despite this little is known about it; even its chronology is debated. This

paper presents the first results of radiocarbon dating of the site. These data allow us to begin to understand the relevance and function of Tingambato, which at the time of its occupation was one of the largest in Western Mexico.

- Source 2 URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/latin-american-antiquity/article/abs/revisitando-las-exploraciones-arqueologicas-en-el-sitio-de-tingambato-michoacan-nuevos-datos-nuevas-tecnologias/F5AD396EDCE31248D3A76802FF0D63FF>
- Source 2 Description: This article presents a review of the findings from the Tingambato site in south-central Michoacán, Mexico, in light of the latest work carried out over the past seven years using recent technologies. We present a complete study of the architecture, the materials, and especially the dates that allow us to finally establish the occupation of this important archaeological site during the first 900 years of our era. Finally, we present a study of the contexts of two impressive tombs found in the archaeological site using virtual reconstructions, photogrammetry, and lidar, which allows us to better understand the funeral customs of the elite sectors of this group.
- Source 3 URL: https://www.laiesken.net/arqueologia/archivo/2023/5202_en
- Source 3 Description: This report shows a first map of the Tingambato archaeological site, which is located in the center of the avocado belt of Michoacan, Mexico. It addresses the problem about the impact of this crop on the archaeological heritage and the possible applications of LiDAR technology for its conservation.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1978-1979 and 2014-2020

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Proyecto Tinganio 1978-1979 and Proyecto Arqueología y PAisaje del Área Centro Sur de Michoacan 2014-2020

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: Cerro Comburinda. This hill is a reference for the construction of the pyramidal mounds

and is aligned with them.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Mound

– Terracing

– Water feature

– Other [specify]: Ball game court, palace complex, tombs

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: It's at the skirts of the town of Tingambato.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: It is surrounded mostly by avocado orchards.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A group of structures:

– Yes

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Social

Notes: The pyramidal structures of the site must have been used for ritual purposes. We have no evidence of sacrificial use.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– I don't know

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– I don't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– I don't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: Tomb 1 of Tingambato is very important because a large number of people were found in this tomb, we believe that it is a single family group, but in this sense, DNA studies are currently being conducted to corroborate this hypothesis.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: The main hypothesis of government at Tingambato is that this city was ruled by either an individual or an elite group that occupied the central part of the city very close to the pyramidal structures and the ball court.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Location

Notes: It is impossible to know, but the location of the city is in a very important region between the Tierra Caliente and the Meseta Purépecha, which makes it a very relevant place in the regional geography.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The two main pyramids reflect the hills on the horizon, reproducing a sort of sacred landscape.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Under the largest room of the palace complex is Tomb 1, in which a large number of people were buried with rich offerings. Likewise, Tomb 2, where a young woman was found with an offering of 19,000 objects, was covered by a small pyramid.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The palace-like complex seems to be different from the rest of the spaces of the city, besides being self-contained with few accesses to the public zones of the plazas, pyramids, platforms and the ball game.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 2

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 1200

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: There are nearby flagstone mines that were used for the construction of buildings and especially tombs.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Talud Tablero decoration

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Talud tablero

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: One of the most important features of the site are the tombs that have been found.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– I don't know

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– I don't know

Notes: Although the young woman buried in Tomb 2 with 19,000 objects and since she was found alone in the chamber seems to have been treated very differently from the rest of the tombs containing multiple burials.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– I don't know

Notes: We think not, but DNA studies are being done to better determine this.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: The objects found in the tombs are very rich. Necklaces of amazonite and shell,

hundreds of vessels, shells, pyrite mirrors, among many other objects.

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: The objects found in the tombs are very rich. Necklaces of amazonite and shell, hundreds of vessels, shells, pyrite mirrors, among many other objects.

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Notes: The objects found in the tombs are very rich. Necklaces of amazonite and shell, hundreds of vessels, shells, pyrite mirrors, among many other objects.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: The tombs are highly standardized. It is a subterranean construction of a room of 3.5 sides enclosed with a 2m high slab dome. The access to this one was by means of a stairway and they had a door, for its reuse surely, at least this for Tomb 1.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: There are public spaces for ritual in plaza 1 and the ball game.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Probably. The tombs have access stairways, which makes us think that these were reused and rituals were carried out in them.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

- Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

- Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

- Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

- Yes

Notes: Yes, in the tombs. These have a large number of objects

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

- Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

- Yes

Notes: Some of the vessels found as well as certain objects inside the tombs could be summarized in the following way

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

- Yes

Notes: The offerings found come from the localized tombs, which were excavated inside the platform of the last construction stage.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place lease out tools:

– Yes

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Tingambato, Punzo Díaz, Jose Luis. "Revisitando Las Exploraciones Arqueológicas En El Sitio De Tingambato, Michoacán: Nuevos Datos, Nuevas Tecnologías". *Latin American Antiquity* 33, no. 1 (2022): 79-96. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2021.65>.